

Condensation of *p*-Chloroaniline with Formaldehyde in Aqueous Oxalic Acid. A Reinvestigation

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In continuation of our earlier findings¹, we studied the reaction of formaldehyde with *p*-chloroaniline with a view to reexamining the earlier work of Wagner *et al.*² and Farrar³, wherein the reactions involving particularly the *para*-substituted amines led to a number of products, many of which appear not to have been isolated or characterised. The present communication describes the isolation and characterisation of 6-chloro-3-(*p*-chloro)phenyl-1-*N*-methyl-1,2,3,4-tetrahydroquinazoline (1) and 6-chloro-3-(*p*-chloro)phenyl-1,2,3,4-tetrahydroquinazoline-1-carbaldehyde (2) along with the two previously reported quinazoline derivatives, 3 and 4 as the reaction products.

- (1) R = CH₃
(2) R = CHO
(3) R = H

Results and Discussion

Condensation of *p*-chloroaniline with formaldehyde in aqueous oxalic acid at 105° yielded two new crystalline bases 1 and 2, along with two previously reported compounds 3 and 4. Neither the hydroxymethyl base (5), m.p. 138°, reported by Wagner² nor the pseudo-base (6) reported by Farrar³, was isolated.

The constitutions of 1 and 2 were established on the basis of analytical and spectral data. The ¹H nmr spectrum of 1 indicated the presence of two methylenes at δ 4.50

and 4.40 (2H, s each), one N-methyl at 2.86 (3H, s), besides the aromatic protons at 6.55–7.25 (7H, m). Similarly, the ir spectrum of 2 showed the absence of hydroxy and amino groups, but the presence of a carbonyl group was observed at 1 682 cm⁻¹. The ¹H nmr spectrum of 2 indicated the presence of two methylenes at δ 4.55 and 5.18 (2H, s each), one formyl group at 8.72 (1H, s), besides the aromatic protons at 6.85–7.20 (7H, m). Both the structures of 6-chloro-3-(*p*-chloro)phenyl-1-*N*-methyl-1,2,3,4-tetrahydroquinazoline (1) and 6-chloro-3-(*p*-chloro)phenyl-1,2,3,4-tetrahydroquinazoline-1-carbaldehyde (2) are in agreement with the mass spectral data. Furthermore, alkaline hydrolysis of the N-formyl derivative (2) yielded the expected tetrahydroquinazoline (3), thus lending further support to the structure 2.

The two other products were identified as 3 and 4 by usual comparative studies.

Experimental

M.p.s. were obtained using a Gallenkamp apparatus. Ir spectra (KBr) were obtained on a Pye-Uni. SP3-200 spectrophotometer. ¹H nmr spectra on a Varian spectrometer (80 MHz) and mass spectra on a V.G. Micromass 7070H spectrometer.

Reaction of *p*-chloroaniline: A mixture of *p*-chloroaniline (3.81 g, 0.03 mol) and formalin (39%; 9 ml) was added to warm oxalic acid (0.5 g in 2.5 ml water) and the mixture was heated at 105° for 4 h under nitrogen. The product was worked up in the usual way to give a mixture of four compounds (tlc, benzene-ethylacetate). These were separated by chromatography over neutral alumina using benzene-ethyl acetate (9.5 : 0.5, v/v) as eluent. The first fraction gave the base (1) as white crystalline solid (0.8 g, 21%), m.p. 109–10° (ethyl acetate); *R*_f 0.55 (toluene-ethyl acetate). (Found: C, 61.39; H, 4.01; N, 9.51. C₁₅H₁₄Cl₂N₂ requires: C, 61.43; H, 4.09; N, 9.55%); *m/z* 296, 294, 292 (*M*⁺), 291 (100), 277, 166.

The second fraction gave 2 as a white crystalline solid (0.6 g, 16%), m.p. 86–87° (petroleum ether-ethyl acetate); *R*_f 0.45 (toluene-ethyl acetate, 10 : 1.5), (Found: C, 58.76; H, 3.91; N, 9.08. C₁₅H₁₂Cl₂N₂O requires: C, 58.82; H, 3.92; N, 9.15%); *m/z* 310, 308, 306 (*M*⁺), 277, 152, 117, 75.

The third fraction furnished 3 as the major product (1.5 g, 39%), m.p. 159–60° (ethyl acetate-hexane) (lit.² 158–

159°); $\nu_{\max}$ 3282 cm^{-1} (NH); δ (CDCl_3) 4.4 (2H, s, $-\text{CH}_2-\text{N}-$), 4.55 (2H, s, $\text{NH}-\text{CH}_2$), 4.68 (1H, br, NH), 6.78–7.4 (7H, ArH). The last fraction gave the dihydroquinazoline (4) as a white crystalline solid (0.40 g, 11%), m.p. 185–86° (ethyl acetate) (lit.² 186–87°).

Conversion of 2 to 3: A solution of 2 (0.2 g) in 10% ethanolic NaOH (5 ml) was refluxed on a steam-bath for 30 min. Ethanol was then removed under reduced pressure, the residue diluted with water and extracted with ether. The ethereal layer was washed free of alkalies, dried

(Na_2SO_4) and the removal of solvent under reduced pressure yielded 3 (140 mg, 70%), identified by m.p. and m.m.p.

References

1. V. PEESAPATI, P. L. PAUSON and R. A. PETHRICK, *J Chem Res (S)*, 1987, 194
2. E. C. WAGNER and A. EISNER, *J Am Chem. Soc.*, 1937 **59**, 879; T. R. MILLER and E. C. WAGNER, *J Am Chem Soc.*, 1941, **63**, 832.
3. W. V. FARRAR, *J Appl Chem*, 1964, **14**, 389.